

Event-Defined Recurrence in Neural Population State Space

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Abstract

Neuroimaging time series can be represented as trajectories through a state space, where each point describes the joint activity of the recorded neural population. We propose that sensory events reshape local state space geometry, biasing subsequent trajectories toward event-associated regions. We formalize this using a conformal deformation of state space geometry and show an associated increase in trajectory residence time near event-defined regions in synthetic data. We then tested whether visual omission events define reproducible regions of population state space in calcium imaging recordings from mouse primary visual cortex. In Novel 1 sessions, a focus was defined from a subset of omissions and held-out omissions were compared against matched controls. Held-out omissions lay closer to this focus in 87 of 88 plane-by-principal component comparisons and showed greater dwell time near the focus in 88 of 88 comparisons. Omission recurrence exceeded shuffled-event recurrence in all comparisons, confirming the effect was not explained by generic task-event structure. These results show that low-dimensional population state spaces can capture event-defined recurrence structure in cortical activity, consistent with the proposed geometric framework.

Introduction

Neural population activity can be modelled as a trajectory through state space, where each point represents a configuration of recorded population activity^{1,2}. This framework has been used to characterize population dynamics in motor control, decision-making, and context-dependent computation^{3,4}, often combined with dimensionality-reduction techniques that reveal task-related structure in high-dimensional data⁵. A key open question is whether sensory events only evoke transient responses, or whether they also bias subsequent population activity toward event-associated regions of state space.

Visual cortical activity is shaped by prior experience and expectation, not only by current input. Repeated exposure to a stimulus set reshapes excitatory and VIP inhibitory responses in mouse visual cortex⁶, and early visual cortical activity changes when input is unexpected or absent despite expectation⁷⁻⁹. Omission paradigms exploit this directly: neural activity can be measured in response to a withheld expected stimulus, isolating internally structured activity from bottom-up visual input.

Prior work has shown that omitted visual events modulate activity in visual cortex and related circuits, though the timing and interpretation of these responses vary across regions and paradigms^{8,10,11}. These studies have asked whether activity responds at the time of omission, but whether omissions also define reproducible regions of state space to which subsequent activity returns has yet to be examined.

Here we propose a geometric account of state space recurrence. We formalize sensory events as locally transforming state space geometry, biasing subsequent trajectories toward event-associated regions. We show in synthetic data that a conformal deformation of state space geometry increases dwell time near event-defined regions. We then test whether omissions define reproducible regions of state space in calcium imaging recordings from mouse primary visual cortex. We ask whether held-out omissions return activity toward an omission-defined focus more strongly than matched controls and whether this recurrence depends on the animal's experience with the stimulus set.

Methods

Flat state space: We consider a neural activity variable $q(t)$ evolving under a second-order equation of motion:

$$\ddot{q} = f(q, \dot{q}, u) \quad (1)$$

where $u(t)$ denotes external sensory input.

We write the corresponding state space trajectory as:

$$x(t) = (q(t), \dot{q}(t)) \quad (2)$$

We assume henceforth that both q and \dot{q} have been normalized by characteristic scales, so that the resulting dimensionless coordinates span a Euclidean state space metric:

$$ds^2 = dq^2 + d\dot{q}^2 \quad (3)$$

As such, the baseline dynamics in Eq. (1) evolve within the flat geometry in Eq. (3).

Warped state space: We now localize a sensory event at a point p in state space. Using Eq. (2), the local effect of the sensory event is represented by a scalar field centered on this point:

$$\phi(x) = -\gamma e^{-\|x-p\|^2/2\sigma^2} \quad (4)$$

where $\gamma > 0$ and $\sigma > 0$ control the strength and spatial extent of the warping in state space, respectively.

The event-associated geometry is then obtained by using the field in Eq. (4) to warp the Euclidean metric in Eq. (3):

$$ds^2 = e^{2\phi(x)}(dq^2 + d\dot{q}^2) \quad (5)$$

The conformal factor satisfies $e^{2\phi(x)} < 1$ near p , as $\phi(x) < 0$. In the model, a sensory event is represented as a local contraction of state space around the event-associated point p .

Single-trajectory warp deflection: The Riemannian energy associated with the warped metric in Eq. (5) is given by

$$E = \int e^{2\phi(x)} \|\dot{x}\|^2 dt \quad (6)$$

where (using Eq. (1))

$$\dot{x}(t) = (\dot{q}, f) \quad (7)$$

is the tangent vector of the state space trajectory in Eq. (2).

Applying the Euler-Lagrange equation to Eq. (6) we obtain the geometric acceleration:

$$a_{geo} = \|\dot{x}\|^2 \nabla \phi - 2(\dot{x} \cdot \nabla \phi) \dot{x} \quad (8)$$

Evaluating Eq. (8) along the baseline flow in Eq. (7) and retaining the second component of a_{geo} , corresponding to the acceleration coordinate of the state space trajectory, gives the geometric correction term to the baseline acceleration:

$$\Delta f = (\dot{q}^2 + f^2) \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \dot{q}} - 2f \left(\dot{q} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial q} + f \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \dot{q}} \right) \quad (9)$$

We then model the event-related geometric effect by treating the geometric correction Δf in Eq. (9) as a first-order perturbation of the baseline acceleration f in Eq. (1):

$$\ddot{q} = f + \lambda \Delta f \quad (10)$$

where $0 < \lambda < 1$ controls the strength of the perturbation.

This gives the central claim of the model: sensory events locally modify the effective geometry of state space, which in turn results in an additive correction to the baseline neural dynamics.

Synthetic data: To provide a numerical proof of concept, we used a van der Pol oscillator as the baseline system in Eq. (1)

$$f = \mu(1 - q^2)\dot{q} - \omega^2 q \quad (11)$$

where μ controls the nonlinear damping and ω is the angular frequency. This system was chosen because it has a stable limit cycle and spatially varying state space divergence $\mu(1 - q^2)$, allowing the event-induced geometric correction to interact with a non-uniform baseline flow.

A focal point p was placed on the limit cycle and the conformal field ϕ was defined as in Eq. (4), with width parameter σ . Trajectories were initialized outside the event-associated region and allowed to evolve under both baseline and warped conditions. Residence near p was defined as $\tau = \int_0^T P_{event}(t) dt$, where $P_{event}(t)$ is the proportion of trajectories within a distance σ of point p at time t . This yielded residence τ_{base} and τ_{warp} under baseline and warped conditions.

To test whether any increase in residence time was specific to the event-associated region, we generated a spatial null distribution. Control points were identified by uniformly sampling the state space and retaining points that were at least 3σ from p and had baseline residence times within 20% of τ . For each retained control point, we computed the corresponding warped-to-baseline residence ratio and compared the event-associated residence ratio against this null distribution.

Empirical data: We tested the recurrence prediction using public Allen Visual Behavior Optical Physiology (Ophys) data. This dataset consists of *in vivo* two-photon calcium imaging recordings from mouse visual cortex during a visual change-detection task. Mice viewed a continuous sequence of briefly presented natural images and were trained to lick in response to image changes to receive water reward. The dataset includes active-behavior sessions, passive-viewing sessions, repeated familiar-image sessions, and sessions involving novel image sets.

We focused on active-behavior recordings from primary visual cortex (VISp) because visual omissions provide a clear task-defined event in a sensory cortical area and because image identity provides a stimulus-defined positive control for the state-space analysis. We restricted the analysis to excitatory-cell recordings from Slc17a7-IRES2-Cre mice and excluded imaging planes with fewer than 20 recorded cells.

The main empirical analyses used 22 VISp imaging planes from 9 mice in Novel 1 sessions, in which animals were exposed to a given image set for the first time. An additional 26 VISp imaging planes from 9 mice in Familiar sessions, in which the image set had been previously experienced, were analyzed to assess whether the recurrence effect depended on experience level. Seven mice contributed both a Novel 1 and a Familiar session, allowing a paired within-animal comparison. Each imaging plane corresponds to one cortical depth within a session; multi-plane sessions therefore provide recordings from multiple VISp depths within the same animal.

Omission events: The visual task includes image presentations at regular task-defined times. On a subset of scheduled presentations, the image is omitted (omission events). A repeatable neural pattern around an omission event therefore cannot be attributed simply to direct retinal input by a newly presented image. Instead, omission-aligned activity can reflect internally structured task timing, expectation, or ongoing population dynamics.

For each experiment, omission times were extracted from the Allen stimulus presentation table. Non-omitted, non-change image presentations were used as matched control events. These controls were selected to provide ordinary task events that occurred within the same session but did not correspond to omitted scheduled stimuli.

Empirical state space: At each imaging frame, the activity of all recorded cells defined a high-dimensional population vector with dimensionality equal to the number of cells in a given imaging plane. Following normalization, the empirical state space was defined using principal component (PC) analysis of dF/F activity. The analysis was repeated using 5, 10, 20, and 50 principal components to ensure that the result was not dependent on a single dimensionality choice.

Omission recurrence test: For each experiment, omission events were divided into training and testing subsets. The training omissions were used to define an omission-associated focus in PC state space, computed as the mean population state in a fixed peri-omission window around the training omission times. The remaining omissions were not used to define the focus and were held out for testing. This cross-validation step tested whether new omission events returned to the omission-defined region without reusing the same events that defined the region.

For each held-out omission and matched control event, we computed the distance from the population trajectory to the omission focus, together with dwell near the omission focus. A local neighborhood around the focus was defined using a distance threshold estimated from stimulus-window distances in the same experiment. Dwell was then computed as the fraction of peri-event time spent inside this neighborhood.

Bootstrap inference: Statistical uncertainty was estimated by bootstrap resampling. On each iteration, held-out omission events and matched control events were resampled, and the distance and dwell differences were recomputed. This yielded bootstrap confidence intervals and one-sided empirical p-values for the positive recurrence direction. The analysis was repeated independently for each experiment, signal representation, and number of principal components.

Shuffled-event control: To test whether omission recurrence exceeded generic task-event recurrence, we performed a shuffled-event control in which event labels were shuffled to define a comparison focus from task events that preserved session structure but removed specific omission identity. The same recurrence analysis was then applied to this shuffled focus.

Image-identity positive control: As a positive control, we tested whether the same PC state-space method could detect known visual structure. For each image identity, a focus was defined from one subset of image presentations, and held-out presentations of the same image were compared with presentations of other images. Because VISp is expected to contain image-related population structure, successful image-identity recurrence provides a control showing that the state-space method can recover meaningful sensory organization in the data.

Results

Synthetic data: To provide a numerical proof of concept, we simulated trajectories evolving under a van der Pol baseline system with and without the geometric correction induced by the conformally warped metric. Starting from the same initial condition, the baseline and warped trajectories followed similar limit-cycle dynamics but diverged locally as they approached the event-associated focus (Fig. 1A). Across multiple trajectories initialized from different starting points, the conformally warped dynamics increased residence near the focus. Dwell time within one σ of the focus increased by 5.0% under warped compared with baseline dynamics (Fig. 1B). This increase was unlikely under a spatial null distribution constructed from control regions far from the focus with matched baseline dwell times ($p = 0.006$). Thus, the conformally warped metric produced a small but statistically robust increase in time spent near the event-associated focus.

Figure 1. Simulation of event-associated recurrence under a conformally warped state-space metric.

A) Example van der Pol trajectories in state space under baseline dynamics (black) and warped dynamics (red). Both trajectories begin from the same initial condition. Concentric rings mark distances of σ and 2σ from the event-associated focus. The inset shows the region near the focus where the baseline and warped trajectories begin to diverge.

B) Cumulative dwell time near the event-associated focus across multiple trajectories. Warped dynamics increased residence near the focus relative to baseline dynamics.

Empirical data:

We tested whether omitted visual events define reproducible regions of VISp population state space. A subset of omission events was used to define a focus in PC state space, and held-out omissions were compared with matched non-omission controls by distance to the focus and by dwell within its local neighborhood.

In Novel 1 sessions, held-out omissions returned closer to the focus than matched controls across 22 imaging planes from 9 mice, tested at 5, 10, 20, and 50 PCs. The distance contrast was positive in 87 of 88 plane-by-PC comparisons (mean 0.819), and all 22 planes showed positive distance recurrence when averaged across PC counts (Fig. 2A). Dwell near the focus was also greater for held-out omissions than controls in 88 of 88 comparisons (mean 0.152), reaching one-

sided bootstrap significance in 84 of 88 comparisons. All 22 planes showed positive dwell recurrence when averaged across PC counts (Fig. 2B).

Omission recurrence exceeded shuffled-event recurrence in all Novel 1 comparisons (Fig. 2C). The mean omission distance contrast was 0.819 versus 0.163 for the shuffled-event control (mean difference 0.657), and the omission dwell contrast was 0.152 versus 0.030 (mean difference 0.122). The effect was therefore not explained by generic task-event structure.

Figure 2. Omission recurrence in VIsP population state space. Each number represents one imaging plane averaged across PC counts; mouse identity is indicated by number (1–9); the dashed vertical line shows the mean.

A) Distance recurrence in Novel 1 sessions. Positive values indicate held-out omissions lay closer to the omission-defined focus than matched controls.

B) Dwell recurrence in Novel 1 sessions. Positive values indicate held-out omissions spent more peri-event time near the focus than matched controls.

C) Specificity control. Values show omission distance contrast minus shuffled-event distance contrast; positive values indicate the omission-defined focus produced stronger recurrence than a shuffled-event focus.

The image-identity positive control confirmed that the same analysis detected stimulus-related population structure in VIsP, consistent with established image selectivity in this area⁶. Held-out presentations of the same image returned closer to image-defined foci than presentations of other images, with a mean distance contrast of 0.503 across Novel 1 planes, and all 22 planes showed positive image-identity recurrence.

Familiar sessions showed weaker and more heterogeneous recurrence. Across 26 imaging planes from 9 mice, the mean distance contrast was 0.092 and the mean dwell contrast was 0.016, substantially smaller than the Novel 1 effects. At the plane level, 13 of 26 showed positive distance recurrence and 17 of 26 showed positive dwell recurrence. Seven mice contributed both Novel 1 and Familiar sessions, and in all 7 both distance and dwell recurrence were larger in Novel 1 than Familiar (mean paired distance difference 0.771, mean paired dwell difference 0.143; one-sided Wilcoxon signed-rank, $p = 0.0078$ for each). Omission recurrence was thus strongest during first exposure to the image set, suggesting its strength depends on experience with the stimulus environment.

Discussion

We propose that sensory events may not only evoke transient responses but also reshape local state-space geometry, biasing subsequent population trajectories toward event-associated regions. We illustrate this in principle with a simple conformal-warp simulation, wherein local contraction around a focus is sufficient to produce measurable recurrence and increased dwell of subsequent trajectories near that region. The Allen Visual Behavior Ophys data support the corresponding empirical prediction — omitted visual events define reproducible regions of population state space, and held-out omissions return to these regions more than shuffled task events do.

The result adds a state-space perspective to an established literature on omission responses in visual cortex. Prior work has shown that omitting an expected visual stimulus drives reliable activity in mouse V1, with the strength of this response increasing with experience in a familiar environment^{8,10}. More recently, the diversity of omission responses across brain-wide circuits was characterized, showing that hippocampal and subcortical regions contribute to omission detection beyond visual cortex¹¹. These prior studies have asked whether neural activity changes at the time of omission, whereas our analysis asks a different question: do omissions define a reproducible region of population state space to which later activity returns? Our framing also connects to work on event structure and neural population dynamics beyond visual cortex. Kanter et al. (2025) recently showed that event boundaries in lateral entorhinal cortex cause discrete shifts in population trajectory, segmenting neural activity into temporal units with recurring structure across multiple timescales¹².

Our observation that recurrence was stronger in Novel 1 than Familiar sessions warrants careful interpretation. A simple accumulation-of-experience account would predict the opposite: that repeated exposure to the same image set would strengthen a stable omission focus over time. One interpretation of this counter-intuitive result is that omission recurrence is strongest when the stimulus environment is newly encountered, because omitted events are more salient, more disruptive to ongoing sensory processing, or more informative about the structure of a new image set. In familiar sessions, omissions may be less distinct from general task timing or absorbed into a more stable learned task representation, reducing the specificity of the omission-defined focus. This interpretation is consistent with findings that visual cortical responses to unexpected stimuli are strongest in mice with limited experience of the relevant environment¹⁰, and that familiarity modulates both excitatory and inhibitory response dynamics in VISp⁶.

The relationship between the conformal-warp simulation and the empirical result should be stated precisely. The Allen data do not estimate a metric tensor or fit a conformal factor, and the model is therefore not implied as a mechanism. Its role is instead to show that local state-space contraction is sufficient to produce the recurrence signature observed in the data, providing a minimal generative account of how such structure could arise.

In summary, omitted visual events define recurrent population states in mouse primary visual cortex, and this recurrence is specific to omission structure rather than to generic task-event timing. The conformal-warp framework offers a geometric account of how such recurrence could arise. Together, the model and data support a view in which meaningful sensory events are represented not only by changes in firing or fluorescence, but by reproducible regions of population state space that subsequent dynamics preferentially revisit.

Data availability

The two-photon murine data is made available at the following repository:
https://allensdk.readthedocs.io/en/latest/visual_behavior_optical_physiology.html

Code availability

All code used in this study is made available at the following repository:
<https://github.com/allavailablepubliccode/recurrence>

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